

Title: Genetic Copy Number Variants, Cognition and Psychosis: A Meta-analysis and a Family Study

Running Title: Copy number variants and cognition

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Abstract

The burden of large and rare copy number genetic variants (CNVs) as well as certain specific CNVs increase the risk of developing schizophrenia. Several cognitive measures are purported schizophrenia endophenotypes and may represent an intermediate point between genetics and the illness. This paper investigates the influence of CNVs on cognition. We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of the literature exploring the effect of CNV burden on general intelligence. We included 10 primary studies with a total of 18,847 participants and found no evidence of association. In a new psychosis family study, we investigated the effects of CNVs on specific cognitive abilities. We examined the burden of large and rare CNVs (>200Kb, <1% MAF) as well as known schizophrenia-associated CNVs in patients with psychotic disorders, their unaffected relatives and controls (N=3,428) from the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium (PEIC). The carriers of specific schizophrenia-associated CNVs showed poorer performance than non-carriers in immediate ($P= 0.0036$) and delayed ($P= 0.0115$) verbal recall. We found suggestive evidence that carriers of schizophrenia-associated CNVs had poorer block design performance ($P=0.0307$). We do not find any association between CNV burden and cognition. Our findings show that the known high-risk CNVs are not only associated with schizophrenia and other neurodevelopmental disorders, but are also a contributing factor to impairment in cognitive domains such as memory and perceptual reasoning, and act as intermediate biomarkers of disease risk.

Introduction

Copy number variants (CNVs) occur if sections of DNA sequence become deleted or duplicated¹⁻³. Although many CNVs are benign and contribute to natural human variation⁴, larger and rarer variants are more likely to be pathogenic and under negative selection pressure^{5,6}. The phenotypic effects of CNVs are not fully understood, but they influence neurodevelopment, cognitive abilities and the risk of several common brain disorders⁶.

Specific CNV loci are associated with increased risk of developing schizophrenia⁷⁻¹¹. A recent large CNV meta-analysis by the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium showed robust genome-wide significant associations for eight loci as well as suggestive support for an additional nine¹². Schizophrenia-associated CNVs have incomplete penetrance^{6,13}, and are rare, hence most people with schizophrenia are not carriers. However, schizophrenia-associated CNVs have odds ratios ranging from 2 to 30^{12,14} and thus constitute some of the strongest known risk factors for the illness.

An increased burden of large and rare CNVs has also been associated with schizophrenia^{15,16}. Studies have shown that, compared to healthy controls, individuals with schizophrenia carry a greater number of rare (<1% frequency) CNVs of over 20 kilobases (Kb)¹², 100 Kb¹⁵⁻¹⁷, 200 Kb^{16,17}, 500 Kb^{16,17} and one Mb¹⁸. The largest study to date, by the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium, further shows that the burden is enriched for genes associated with synaptic function and that deletions assert greater effect than duplications¹². Despite strong evidence that CNVs are risk factors for schizophrenia and other developmental disorders, the mechanisms by which CNVs lead to disease onset remain unclear.

Endophenotypes are biomarkers that characterise illnesses and indicate genetic liability, as intermediate steps on the pathway from genes to disease^{19,20}. Cognitive function is one such endophenotype for schizophrenia and extensive literature shows that individuals with schizophrenia

display reduced performance across a range of tests of specific and general cognition^{21,22}. This is not simply due to the effects of antipsychotic medication²³, and nor is it just an epiphenomenon of the symptoms of schizophrenia; cognition is impaired before illness onset^{24,25} as well as amongst the unaffected relatives of patients with schizophrenia²⁶⁻²⁸. A recent genome wide association study with more than 269,000 samples shows a bidirectional effect with intelligence having a strong protective effect towards schizophrenia risk, and a smaller reverse effect, with schizophrenia predisposing to impaired cognitive functioning²⁹.

IQ and general cognitive ability are heritable^{30,31,32,33}; however despite the identification of 205 loci affecting over 1,000 genes associated with intelligence²⁹, they only explain approximately 5% of the inter-individual variability in intelligence. Part of the unexplained heritability of intelligence could be attributable to copy number variants. Many CNVs affect genes involved in neurodevelopment^{15,34,35}, providing a mechanism by which specific CNVs and CNV burden could affect cognition.

There is evidence linking several specific CNVs with schizophrenia, other neurodevelopmental disorders, educational attainment^{36,37} and with impaired cognition; ^{38,39,40,41}. Furthermore, Stefansson et al.⁴² showed that healthy carriers of any of 26 neuropsychiatric CNVs collectively performed at an intermediate level between healthy non-carriers and schizophrenia patients in several cognitive tests. This indicates that, while the risk CNVs may not have full penetrance for disease, most carriers will exhibit some degree of phenotypic change such as impaired cognition. A large study on the UK Biobank further supports this effect of neuropsychiatric CNVs impairing cognition in healthy carriers³⁷.

While the detrimental effects of specific schizophrenia-associated CNVs on cognition are well characterised, the influence of CNV burden on cognition is less clear. Some evidence, both in clinical samples and healthy populations, suggests that increased CNV burden is associated with lower

IQ^{30,31,43,44}, while other studies have failed to find this association^{35,45–47}. Until now, few studies have reported the effects of schizophrenia-associated CNVs or CNV burden on specific cognitive abilities^{37,42,48}.

Firstly, we conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of the literature examining the relationship between CNV burden and general cognitive ability. We then present data from a new family study from the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium (PEIC)⁴⁹ investigating the influence of CNVs (both burden and loci) on cognitive endophenotypes for schizophrenia^{27,50}.

Methods

Meta-Analysis of published association studies of CNVs and general IQ

We conducted a literature search using the databases Pubmed, Medline, and PsychINFO using the following search terms: "(CNV* OR copy number OR copy-number) AND (IQ OR intelligence OR cogniti*)". The time window included any papers published before 1st April 2019. The reference and citations lists of relevant papers were examined to identify other relevant papers. We imposed no restriction on participant age, geographical location, or article language.

In addition to IQ, we included papers examining other measures of general intelligence as they are thought to be closely linked⁵¹. Papers investigating both patient and healthy populations were included. Where different papers used the same sample of participants, only the study with the most relevant phenotype was included. If multiple measures of intelligence were included (for example see references ^{47,52}) the one deemed closest to the other studies was used for the meta-analysis. Similarly, if measures for both common and rare CNV-burden were reported⁵² we included the latter for the meta-analysis.

Titles and abstracts of all relevant papers were screened to assess whether they met the inclusion criteria. Where necessary, we contacted the authors to request additional information needed to include the study in the meta-analysis. Supplementary table 1 shows the data extracted from papers.

Meta-analysis of the literature

A random-effects meta-analysis was conducted using StatsDirect version 3.0⁵³ to calculate an overall estimate of the correlation between CNV burden and IQ for the included studies. Where primary studies reported Spearman's correlations or standardised coefficients they were converted to

Pearson's correlation coefficients to ensure the studies were as comparable as possible^{54,55}. A random-effects meta-analysis was chosen due to the variability in methods of the included studies (including different participant samples and inclusion criteria for CNVs). Statistical heterogeneity was measured using Cochran's Q statistic.

CNV analysis of the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium sample

The initial dataset (prior to quality control) included 5597 participants from the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium (PEIC) family study⁴⁹, including people with schizophrenia, bipolar disorder with psychotic symptoms and other forms of psychosis, their unaffected relatives and unrelated controls. Participants were of European ancestry and assessments were conducted at nine centres: Amsterdam, Edinburgh, Groningen, London, Maastricht, Munich, Pamplona, Perth and Utrecht (see supplementary table 2 for further detail). Participants were recruited through clinical teams, voluntary organisations and press advertisements, and contributed both genetic data and cognitive performance measures⁴⁹. All participants provided written informed consent and the study was approved by the respective ethical committees at each of the participating centres. Details of diagnostic classifications can be found in the supplementary methods.

Genotyping and quality control

DNA was obtained from blood for all participants and sent to the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute (Cambridge, United Kingdom). Samples were genotyped with the Human SNP Array 6.0 at the Affymetrix Services Laboratory (www.affymetrix.com). We applied standard quality control procedures as described in the supplement and in Bramon et al⁴⁹. CNVs were identified using PennCNV⁵⁶ and Affymetrix Power Tools, following the PennCNV-Affy protocol⁵⁷ to calculate log R

ratio (LRR) and B-allele frequency (BAF). Standard PennCNV settings were used and data were adjusted for genomic waves⁵⁸ using Affymetrix 6.0 GC-model file.

Individual-based quality control for the CNVs was performed using statistics calculated with PennCNV: Quality control thresholds were determined based on inspection of the frequency distributions of the BAF-drift, LRR-standard deviation, and number of CNVs per participant, respectively. Individuals with either BAF-drift of >0.01, LRR-standard deviation of >0.5 or more than 300 CNV calls were removed. CNV-level quality control was performed by excluding CNVs with 10 or fewer SNPs and by iteratively merging adjacent calls together if the length between calls was <20% of the combined length. Calls made by PennCNV in the pseudo-autosomal regions of the X-chromosome (10,000 – 2,781,479 bp and 155,701,382 – 156,030,895 bp, hg18) were excluded.

All CNVs included in the analysis were visually inspected by two researchers blind to clinical data using an in-house script to visualise BAF and LRR patterns. A consensus decision on inclusion was made between two researchers, both blind to clinical data, based on the comparison of the observed LRR and BAF of the affected region with the expected for a CNV with the given copy state. PennCNV frequently made CNV predictions that did not fit with the expected allelic and/or intensity pattern of the given copy state and thus 72% of CNV calls were discarded.

CNV burden analysis

Only rare (<1% frequency in the sample) and large (>200 Kb) CNVs were included in the CNV burden. Frequency of CNVs were determined by identifying common CNV loci, through independent mapping of start and stop positions of all CNVs. CNVs whose start positions were within 300,000 bp of each other, where the stop position was also within a 300,000 bp bin were considered to be the same loci (see supplementary Figure 1 for details). In addition to calculations using total length of CNVs, we also measured burden as numbers of genes affected, as described in Marshall et al. 2016¹².

We did this by annotating CNVs with RefSeq genes (hg18), including genes where at least one base pair of an exon overlapped with the CNV and adding up all unique genes affected in each individual. Total burden, and deletion and duplication burdens were analysed separately.

Analysis of schizophrenia-associated CNVs:

We searched for carriers of 27 CNVs with good evidence of an association with schizophrenia as described by Marshall et al. 2016¹², Kirov et al. 2014⁶ and Stefansson et al. 2014⁴² (see supplementary table 3). For the analysis of schizophrenia-associated CNVs we considered all samples prior to any sample/CNV level quality control and performed visual inspection of all samples with CNV calls that overlapped with >10% of a schizophrenia-associated locus. Samples identified with true schizophrenia associated CNVs by consensus of two researchers blind to clinical data, were included in the analysis even if they failed sample/CNV level quality control. For 2p16 deletions, all CNV calls overlapping the region were inspected, and participants with validated CNVs affecting exons of the causative gene NRXN1⁵⁹ were identified as carriers.

Cognitive measures

Cognitive measures collected from participants included block design^{60,61} (a test of perceptual reasoning), the combined digit span (measuring attention and working memory), and the Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Task (RAVLT) immediate and delayed recall (measuring short and long term verbal memory, respectively). As different versions of these tests were used across centres, participants' raw scores were converted into percentages by dividing each participant's score by the maximum achievable score and multiplying by 100. Supplementary table 2 details the number of participants for each cognitive measure.

Kinship matrix

The kinship coefficient is a probabilistic estimate that a random gene from a subject is “identical by descent” to a gene in the same locus from another subject. For “n” subjects, these probabilities can be assembled in an n x n “kinship matrix”, which can be used to model the covariance (or “relatedness”) between individuals and the population structure in a dataset. A kinship matrix based on a LD-pruned set of SNPs (102,112 SNPs selected with pruning parameters: $r^2 = 0.2$; window = 1000Kb) was generated using LDAK⁶² and added as a random effect to the linear and logistic mixed model regressions.

Statistical analysis

Firstly, the CNV burden data were not normally distributed showing clear zero-inflation as expected. Therefore we performed a Wilcoxon rank sum test to compare the CNV burden of individuals with and without cognitive data available.

Secondly, the association between the CNV measures and clinical group was investigated. For this analysis, we performed mixed effects logistic regressions with disease status as outcome (either patients versus controls or relatives versus controls), age, gender and study centre as fixed effects and the kinship matrix as a random effect.

Thirdly, the relationships between known schizophrenia-associated CNVs and quantitative cognitive measures were examined using linear mixed models. The outcome variable was the cognitive measure and the predictor was the participants’ carrier status of schizophrenia-associated CNVs (carriers versus non-carriers). Given that schizophrenia-associated CNVs are very rare, with frequencies ranging from 0.01 – 0.3%^{6,42}, only a combined analysis including several such CNVs was feasible. The analysis for a particular cognitive measure was only performed if data from at least 10 carriers of schizophrenia-associated CNVs with cognitive measures were available. Finally, we also

used linear mixed models to investigate the association between cognitive measures and CNV burden. Age, gender, clinical group (patient, relative and control), study centre and a kinship matrix were included as covariates in all linear mixed models. Analyses were performed using R version 3.5.0⁶³. All mixed model regressions including the kinship matrix as a random effect were performed using the lme4qtl R package⁶⁴.

As is standard practice in genetic association studies, we adjusted the significance threshold for multiple testing. We used two different analysis approaches depending on whether the outcome variable was quantitative or categorical. Firstly, for the linear mixed models, we tested the correlations between all the cognitive outcomes and divided the significance threshold (0.05) by the effective number of traits, as per standard method^{65,66}. We investigated four cognitive measures: digit span, block design, RAVLT immediate, RAVLT delayed. These measures were strongly correlated²⁰, particularly, the last two (0.79), which was reflected by a calculation of the eigenvalues for the correlation matrix, which identified the number of effective traits as three. Secondly, for the mixed effects logistic regression analyses investigating categorical clinical group as outcomes, the number of effective traits were two, since we performed separate logistic regressions comparing cases versus controls and relatives versus controls. We present all uncorrected p-values throughout the paper. However, interpretation of what constitute significant findings was based exclusively on the multiple-testing adjusted p-value thresholds of 0.017 (0.05/3 effective traits) for cognition and of 0.025 (0.05/2 effective traits) for clinical group outcomes. All tests performed were two-sided and the R-code used is available upon request from the corresponding author.

Results

Findings from the systematic review and meta-analysis of the literature

The literature search returned 905 results. Screening of titles and abstracts revealed 13 papers that were assessed for eligibility. See PRISMA diagram and details on the literature search in supplementary figure 2. Eleven primary papers of similar quality were found to examine the association between CNV burden and intelligence^{30,31,35,43-47,67,68} (Supplementary Table 1 & 5).

Ten studies, with a total of 18,847 participants, provided the required data to conduct a meta-analysis and were included in the random-effects meta-analysis^{30,35,43-45,67,68}. Forest plots for analyses of length of deletions (N=18,658) and length of duplications (N=18,580) are displayed in Figure 1, additional forest plots can be found in supplementary figure 3.

None of the meta-analyses showed evidence for an association between their measure of CNV burden and IQ. The pooled correlations between IQ and length of deletions or length of duplications were -0.04 (CI = -0.07, -0.01) and -0.002 (CI = -0.02, 0.02) respectively. Cochran's Q-statistic revealed evidence for between-study heterogeneity in the correlation between length of deletions and IQ (χ^2

= 21.56, $P = 0.0058$) and number of deletions and IQ ($\chi^2 = 33.77$, $P < 0.0001$), number of duplications ($\chi^2 = 11.06$, $P = 0.0114$). There was no evidence for study heterogeneity for the other measures.

One study included in the systematic review did not provide data suitable for the meta-analysis. However, its findings are consistent with the meta-analysis since Van Scheltinga et al. 2013⁴⁶ found no association between their measures of CNV burden and IQ.

Results from the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium sample

The full sample consisted of 5,597 participants. 1,303 participants had CNV data failing quality control due to one or more of the following reasons: 1,107 participants had more than 300 CNVs, 478 had B allele frequency (BAF) drift of >0.01 and 400 had Log R ratio standard deviation (LRR-SD) of >0.5 .

In our study, 77% of samples passed stringent quality control criteria for CNV calling. This call rate is comparable to other CNV studies as exemplified by the latest Psychiatric Genomics Consortium CNV large mega-analysis reporting an overall 72% call rate across 43 primary studies¹². The challenges with CNV calling from SNP microarrays, are well known⁶⁹, and is to a large extent technical in origin. SNP microarrays were not originally designed for CNV detection, and although it is possible as demonstrated by numerous publications, CNV detection from SNP arrays is sensitive to quality issues especially with regards to the intensity measures captured by the probes on the assay⁶⁹.

The 23% of samples excluded on quality control grounds did not differ significantly from those included in the study on key parameters including clinical group distribution and sex. The only significant difference was in age, where the excluded samples on average were five years younger (see full details in supplementary table 6). Age is included as a covariate in all analysis.

Of the 4,294 participants who passed quality control, 3,426 were included in the CNV burden analysis as they had at least one cognitive measure and full information on the included covariates. There were no significant differences in CNV burden measures between samples with and without cognitive data available (see supplementary table 7). An additional two participants that failed the CNV burden quality control were identified from two independent blind visual inspections as carriers of schizophrenia-associated CNVs, and included in that analysis (N=3,428). This sample included 769 patients with psychotic disorders (576 with schizophrenia (74.9%), 89 with bipolar disorder (11.6%) and 104 with other psychoses (13.5%)), 646 unaffected relatives and 2,013 healthy controls (see table 1).

In our sample, we identified 29 participants who carried one schizophrenia-associated CNV each (see loci in supplementary table 3). Table 2 shows the analyses of schizophrenia-associated CNVs and cognition, adjusted for age, gender, clinical group, centre and genetic relatedness. We found evidence of an association between schizophrenia-associated CNVs and RAVLT immediate (regression coefficient = -8.0, 95% CI = -13.3 to -2.6, P = 0.0036) and delayed (regression coefficient = -3.3, 95% CI = -5.8, -0.7, P = 0.0015) recall. This indicates that participants with a schizophrenia-associated CNV had a mean RAVLT immediate recall score that was 8.0% lower than non-carriers, as well as a mean RAVLT delayed recall score that was 3.3% lower. We also found suggestive evidence that carriers of a schizophrenia-associated CNV had poorer scores for block design than non-carriers (mean difference = -10.0, 95% CI = -19.2 to -0.9, P = 0.031) but only at the uncorrected level of significance. As a sensitivity analysis we performed the same associations using only patients with a schizophrenia diagnosis, their relatives and healthy controls, see supplementary table 8. In that analysis the association between CNV carrier status and RAVLT immediate recall remained significant (P = 0.004), and we observed a weaker association with RAVLT delayed recall score at the uncorrected significance level (P = 0.025).

Our CNV burden analysis showed that the mean total length of DNA affected by deletions and duplications was 117.8 and 219.1 Kb, respectively and on average 1.8 genes per participant were affected by these CNVs. We did not find evidence for an increased total CNV burden measured as length of DNA affected by CNVs, or as number of genes affected by CNVs, in people with psychosis compared to healthy controls. Since Marshall et al. 2016¹² found that the association between CNV burden and schizophrenia was more significant when indexed as number of genes affected, we focused our subsequent analyses on this measure. For analyses using CNV length see supplementary table 9 & 10.

We found no evidence for an association between the four cognitive measures and any of the three CNV burden measures, see table 2. Stratified analyses were also conducted by group (supplementary table 11), which showed an association between schizophrenia-associated CNVs and RAVLT immediate recall (regression coefficient = -11.8, 95% CI= -20.2 to -3.4, P = 0.006), and a weaker association with the RAVLT delayed recall (P = 0.02) in the patient group but only at the uncorrected level of significance. There was no other evidence for an association between the various cognitive measures and burden when examining the groups separately.

The mixed effects logistic regression suggests that there was no evidence in the difference of having a schizophrenia-associated CNV amongst patients, relatives and controls. Similarly for CNV burden, the number of genes affected by large CNVs did not differ between the three clinical groups. See supplementary table 4 for details of CNV comparisons between clinical groups. Cognitive performance was impaired in patients compared to controls for all variables examined, as expected, and was worse in relatives than controls for block design and digit span. See supplementary table 12 for adjusted analyses.

As a follow-up analysis we examined five loci found to protect carriers from developing schizophrenia^{12,70}. We identified 41 carriers (22q11.21.dup (N=1), 7q11.21.del (N=21), 7q11.21.dup (N=7), 13q12.11.dup (N=7) and Xq28.dup (N=5)), but found no significant association between performance in cognitive tests and carrier status, or in number of carriers between patients, relatives or controls.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate: (1) the influence of CNV burden on general cognitive ability (IQ) based on a systematic review and meta-analysis of the literature and (2) the influence of schizophrenia-associated CNVs and CNV burden on specific cognitive skills in our family study from the Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium.

The meta-analysis of published studies found no associations between any CNV burden measures and overall IQ. The Psychosis Endophenotypes International Consortium (PEIC) sample revealed that carriers of specific schizophrenia-associated CNVs had clear impairments in immediate and delayed verbal recall. Verbal memory performance has been found to index cortical thinning in medial temporal and prefrontal regions in schizophrenia^{71,72} and has been found to be a cognitive predictor of outcome in schizophrenia and first episode psychosis^{73,74} supporting its role as a plausible endophenotype in psychosis. We also found suggestive evidence that carriers of schizophrenia-associated CNVs perform worse in block design although further investigation is needed to verify the link between schizophrenia-associated CNVs and this and similar measures of perceptual reasoning.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first and only meta-analysis investigating the associations between CNV burden and IQ. We found ten relevant studies with a total of 18,847 participants. Evidence suggests that larger and rarer CNVs are more likely to be pathogenic¹⁷. Therefore, we hypothesised that the larger and rarer CNVs would have greater effects on intelligence. However, the primary studies included in our systematic review and meta-analysis did not always follow this pattern. Indeed the four studies, out of nine, that did find association with deletion length and intelligence included CNVs down to 100Kb or smaller. Two of these studies reported on fewer than 80 participants each. The two remaining studies^{52,68} were among the largest available and performed a rigorous quality control. They both found evidence that all of their rare deletion burden measures (CNV length and number of genes affected) resulted in lower IQ. We believe that at least part of the

reason why none of the meta-analyses we performed found association between any of the measures of CNV burden and intelligence, is due to the heterogeneity in the methodology and CNV criteria of the studies conducted in this area, and it seems the field is still in need of a more consistent and stringent way to analyse CNV burden.

Along with Gialluisi et al. 2016⁴⁸, our study is one of the first to report on associations between measures of large and rare CNV burden and performance on specific cognitive tests, and to our knowledge the first to examine this in both patients with psychosis and their unaffected relatives. The main limitation of our family study was the modest sample size, which limited our power to detect very small effects. CNV detection is known to be prone to false positive calls^{75,76}, therefore a strength is the thoroughness taken in calling CNVs, as all calls included in our burden analysis were visually inspected by two researchers blind to all clinical data in order to ensure their accuracy. We discarded 72% of the CNVs predicted by PennCNV after visual inspection, which shows the importance of such checks. In our sample, we found no evidence of selection bias in relation to quality control or to availability of cognitive data. Thus, the percentage of individuals passing CNV quality control was similar between patients, relatives and controls and comparable to that of Marshall et al 2017¹². Furthermore, the CNV burden did not differ between individuals with and without cognitive data available.

Our findings suggest that CNVs have greater effects on specific aspects of cognition rather than on general intelligence. Our family study investigated the burden of large (>200 Kb), rare (<1% frequency) CNVs, which in general are expected to have greater phenotypic effects^{5,12,77} than the smaller and more frequent CNVs included in many of the studies in the meta-analysis. Furthermore, the genetic contribution to IQ increases with age^{78,79}, and in the meta-analysis there was substantial diversity in ages and clinical group examined across the studies. Finally, the relationship between CNV burden and intelligence may vary substantially with clinical status. Indeed, the majority of

studies of the meta-analysis that included patients with neuropsychiatric conditions^{30,31,44,67} found associations between at least one measure of CNV burden and intelligence, whereas the majority of studies examining healthy participants^{35,45,47} did not. However, our family study included 22.5% of participants with psychosis, compared to 0.8% participants in the meta-analysis, and still did not find an association with any burden measures.

Current available studies, including ours, may still be underpowered to detect a small effect of CNV burden on cognition. Furthermore, it is also important to consider the crudity of the current CNV burden measures defined by size and frequency criteria. As our understanding of the phenotypic effects of CNV improves, more specific burden measures targeting neurodevelopment and brain diseases will emerge. Limited power in our PEIC family study is likely to explain why we did not replicate the association between poorer digit-span and schizophrenia-associated CNVs, as reported by Kendall et al 2016³⁷ in the much larger UK Biobank study.

The Rey Verbal Auditory Learning Task (RAVLT) immediate recall and delayed recall, which measures working memory and long-term memory respectively, are robust endophenotypes of schizophrenia²⁷. Thus, as hypothesised, we found they were impaired amongst the carriers of known schizophrenia-associated CNVs in the PEIC family based sample. The existing literature^{37,68,80} as well as our data provide consistent evidence that the carriers of specific CNVs that increase schizophrenia risk have cognitive impairments. It is widely agreed that a better understanding of the genetics of psychosis is essential for developing new diagnostic and therapeutic interventions. Animal and cellular models will provide essential evidence to understand the mechanisms of the implicated genetic loci, but are only available for a few CNVs. Studying endophenotypes in the human *in vivo* is non-invasive and one of the best tools available to elucidate the role and mechanisms of genetic variants that increase the risk of developing neuropsychiatric disorders.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Figure Legend

Figure 1: Forest plots for the meta-analyses investigating length of deletions (N= 18,658) and length of duplications (N=18,580). For additional plots see supplementary figure 3.

Tables

Table 1: Sample description

Characteristic	CNV Carrier (N)	Non-Carrier (N)	Total (N)	CNV Carrier (%)		
Clinical Group						
Controls	16	1997	2013	0.8%		
Relatives	2	644	646	0.3%		
Patients	11	758	769	1.5%		
Centre						
Munich	3	949	952	0.3%		
Perth	6	548	554	1.1%		
London	2	478	480	0.5%		
Maastricht	4	395	399	1.0%		
Amsterdam	4	329	333	1.2%		
Utrecht	5	304	309	1.6%		
Groningen	5	310	315	1.6%		
Pamplona	0	44	44	0.0%		
Edinburgh	0	42	42	0.0%		
Sex						
Males	16	1743	1759	0.9%		
Females	13	1656	1669	0.8%		
Characteristic	CNV Carrier (N)	CNV Carrier (mean/SD)	Non-Carrier (N)	Non-Carrier (mean/SD)	Total (N)	Total (mean/SD)
Age	29	39.9 (15.6)	3399	43.7 (15.9)	3428	43.7 (15.9)
Cognitive Performance						
Block Design	21	50.6 (24.9)	2726	57.4 (23.6)	2747	57.4 (42.0)
Digit Span	5	60.5 (4.5)	1265	50.7 (15.1)	1270	50.7 (9.4)
RAVLT Immediate Recall	24	46.5 (16.6)	1882	54.7 (14.5)	1906	54.6 (14.9)
RAVLT Delayed Recall	24	14.6 (7.8)	1865	17.7 (6.9)	1889	17.7 (6.6)

Abbreviations: RAVLT, Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test. SD, standard deviation.

Demographic information for participants with data on schizophrenia-associated CNVs. Two participants with schizophrenia-associated CNV were identified in the samples failing QC for CNV burden, these were included only in the analysis of schizophrenia-associated CNVs; thus giving a sample of 3428 participants for the analysis of schizophrenia associated CNVs and 3426 for the analysis of CNV burden. CNV carriers refer to individuals who were

identified as carrying a known schizophrenia-associated CNV (see supplementary table 3)

Table 2: Associations between schizophrenia-associated CNVs and CNV burden with cognition

Predictor	Cognitive Measure	Participants (CNV Carrier)	Regression Coefficient	95% CI	Sig.
Schizophrenia-associated CNVs	Block Design	2747 (21)	-10.1	-19.2, -0.9	0.031
	Digit Span	-	-	-	-
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1906 (24)	-8.0	-13.3, -2.6	0.0036
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1889 (24)	-3.3	-5.8, -0.7	0.0115
Genes affected by all CNVs (burden)	Block Design	2747	-0.1	-0.3, 0.1	0.343
	Digit Span	1270	0.03	-0.2, 0.2	0.775
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1906	-0.03	-0.2, 0.1	0.634
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1889	-0.01	-0.1, 0.1	0.854
Genes affected by deletions (burden)	Block Design	2747	-0.4	-0.8, 0.01	0.056
	Digit Span	1270	-0.1	-0.6, 0.3	0.544
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1906	-0.2	-0.5, -0.1	0.0119
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1889	-0.1	-0.2, -0.01	0.0661
Genes affected by duplications (burden)	Block Design	2747	-0.001	-0.2, 0.2	0.992
	Digit Span	1270	0.06	-0.1, 0.3	0.564
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1906	0.02	-0.1, 0.2	0.774
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1889	0.03	-0.04, 0.1	0.412

Associations between known schizophrenia-associated CNVs and CNV burden with cognitive performance. For the schizophrenia associated CNV analysis digit span was not examined as fewer than 10 CNV carriers had available data. CNV burden was measured as number of genes affected by CNVs larger than >200 Kb, with <1% frequency. All analyses are adjusted for the covariates age, sex, clinical group, centre and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix).

Length of deletions

Correlation (95% confidence interval)

Length of duplications

Correlation (95% confidence interval)

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Supplementary methods:

Phenotypes

Relatives and controls were not excluded if they had a personal history of non-psychotic psychiatric disorders (such as depression or anxiety), provided they were well and off psychotropic medication at the time of testing and for the preceding 12 months.

To confirm or rule out a DSM-IV¹ diagnosis, all participants underwent a structured clinical interview with either the Comprehensive Assessment of Symptoms and History², the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM Disorders³, the Schedule for Affective Disorders and Schizophrenia⁴ or the Schedule for Clinical Assessment in Neuropsychiatry, Version 2.0⁵. Participants were excluded if they had a history of neurologic disease or a loss of consciousness due to a head injury.

For the neuropsychological assessment, the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale, revised version⁶ or third edition⁷, were administered to participants. Performance on two subtests was used for analyses: the combined forward and backward digit span (measuring attention and working memory) and block design (measuring spatial visualisation). The Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test⁸, including both immediate and delayed recall (assessing short- and long-term verbal memory, respectively), was also administered. Higher scores on the cognitive tasks indicate better performance. Additional information on the methodology for each site contributing data is reported elsewhere⁹⁻¹⁵.

Genotyping

Genotyping methods and quality control details are described in full in Bramon et al. 2014¹⁶ and below.

DNA Sample Preparation

Genomic DNA obtained from blood for all participants was sent to the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute, Cambridge, United Kingdom. Samples were processed in 96-well plate format and each plate carried a positive and a negative control. DNA concentrations were quantified using a PicoGreen assay (Invitrogen, Life Technologies, Grand Island, New York) and an aliquot assayed by agarose gel electrophoresis. A sample passed quality control if the original DNA concentration was at least 50 ng/mL and the DNA was not degraded.

Genotyping Methodology and Quality Control

To track sample identity, 30 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) including sex chromosome markers were typed on the Sequenom platform before entry to the whole genome genotyping

pipeline. Of the initial 6935 samples, 347 failed quality control due to degraded or insufficient DNA or incorrect sex classification. The remaining samples were sent for genotyping with the Genome-wide Human SNP Array 6.0 at the Affymetrix Services Lab (<http://www.affymetrix.com>).

Data Quality Control

Genotype calling was conducted using the CHIAMO algorithm (^{17,18}) modified for use with the Affymetrix 6.0 genotyping array. A total of 11,610 SNPs with a study-wide missing data rate over 5% were excluded. Another 26,858 SNPs with four or more Mendelian inheritance errors identified with PEDSTATS were removed¹⁹. Additional exclusion criteria were departure from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium ($p < 10^{-6}$) or minor allele frequency (MAF) < 0.02 with 2,404 and 145,097 SNPs removed, respectively. A total of 38,895 SNPs from the X or Y chromosomes or mitochondrial DNA were also excluded from the analysis. Finally, 9,499 poorly genotyped SNPs were removed following visual inspection of the genotyping intensity plots in the program Evoker²⁰.

214 samples were excluded with more than 2% missing data across all SNPs. Another 70 samples were excluded due to divergent genome-wide heterozygosity (inbreeding coefficients were $F > 0.076$ or $F < -0.076$ as estimated with PLINK²¹). Chromosomal sharing was inferred from a genome-wide subset of 71,677 SNPs and from each duplicate pair the sample with the most complete genotype data was kept. 70 duplicates and monozygotic twins were removed by excluding one of each pair of individuals showing identity by descent greater than 95%.

Initial analysis of the genotype data identified a high fraction of samples (approximately 30%), which showed poor signal-to-noise ratio in the genotyping assay. Because the experimental source of the problem was unclear and to ensure a robust set of genotype calls, these samples were removed from further analysis. The sample loss was randomly distributed across the three clinical groups (32% of patients, 30% of relatives and 30% of controls; χ^2 (2 df) = 3.2; $P = 0.20$).

After SNP quality control and CNV quality control as described in method section, 5,597 individuals remained. The current study included a subset of this larger sample, comprising 3,428 individuals who also had the relevant phenotypic and genetic data available.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: Description of primary studies included in systematic review and meta-analysis

Study	Participants	Number of participants	Mean age (SD)	Measure of Intelligence/ Cog.	Genotyping Array	CNV Length & Freq.	CNV Measures	Statistical Analysis	Outcome
Bagshaw et al. 2013 ²²	Population birth cohort from the Christchurch Health and Development Study.	723 (567 with WISC-R Total IQ score)	Exact values not given. Participants assessed at ages 8-9, 13, 18, and 25.	IQ assessed with WISC-R age 8-9. TOSCA age 13. BWRT age 18. Measure of overall academic achievement age 25.	Illumina Human660W-Quad BeadChip array.	>2 markers. <5% frequency.	CNV count, duplication length, deletion length.	Pearson's correlations.	No significant associations.
Yeo et al. 2011 ²³	Alcohol dependence.	74	39.9 (9.2)	IQ calculated from vocabulary and matrix reasoning subtests of WASI-I.	Illumina Human1M-Duo BeadChip array.	No minimum length specified. <5% frequency.	Duplication count, deletion count, duplication length, deletion length.	Pearson's correlations. Regressions controlling for sex, ethnicity, and interactions of CNV burden with sex and ethnicity.	Correlations: Negative association between deletion length and IQ ($r = -0.30$, $P = 0.010$). Non-significant trend towards association between deletion count and IQ ($r = 0.21$, $P = 0.080$). Regressions: Negative association between deletion length and IQ, for CNVs of <5% ($p < 0.001$), <3% ($P = <0.001$) and <1% ($P = 0.013$) frequency.
McRae et al. 2013 ²⁴	Unrelated healthy participants from the Genetics of twin cognition study.	800	16.5 (1.2)	IQ calculated from short version of the MAB.	Illumina 610K SNP array.	>20 Kb. <5% frequency.	CNV count, duplication count, deletion count, CNV length, duplication length, deletion length.	Pearson's correlations.	No significant associations.
Kirkpatrick et al. 2014 ²⁵	Healthy participants from the Minnesota Twin Family Study (2 different aged twin cohorts and parents), and the Sibling Interaction and Behaviour Study (parents, siblings, adoptees, and step-parents).	6199 (2879 parents, 1015 17yr old twins, 1777 11yr old twins, 358 siblings, 95 adoptees, 75 step-parents.)	Parents = 43.4 (5.5); 17yr old twins = 17.5 (0.5); 11yr old twins = 11.8 (0.4); siblings = 14.9 (1.9); adoptees = 15.3 (2.2); step-parents = 40.7 (7.5)	IQ calculated from abbreviated versions of WISC-R (for participants <16 yr) and WAIS-R (for participants >16yr).	Illumina Human660W-Quad BeadChip array.	>15 markers. <5% frequency.	CNV count, duplication count, deletion count, CNV length, duplication length, deletion length, homozygous deletion count, homozygous deletion length.	Regressions controlling for sex, birth year, and population stratification. Reported Pearson's correlations but not significance levels for correlations.	Regressions: Negative association between duplication length IQ ($P = 0.016$) (not significant after correction for multiple testing). Non-significant trend towards association between duplication count and IQ ($\beta = 0.074$, $P = 0.053$).
Martin et al.	Patients with schizophrenia	78	Information not given.	Full scale IQ, verbal IQ, and performance IQ	Affymetrix Genome-	>10 Kb.	Deletion length	Spearman's correlations.	Negative association between deletion length and full scale IQ ($r = -0.267$, $P = 0.018$), verbal IQ ($r = -$

2014 ²⁶	from Australian subsample of Levinson et al. (2011) GWAS.			calculated from WASI-I. Premorbid IQ estimated with NART.	wide Human SNP array 6.0.	<1% frequency.			0.303, P = 0.007), and premorbid IQ (r = -0.249, P = 0.029).
Langley et al. 2011 ²⁷	Children with ADHD.	Original study: 525. Burden analysis: 520.	10.6 (2.8)	IQ calculated from WISC. Participants aged <12 tested with the WORD (a test of reading ability).	Illumina Human660W-Quad BeadChip array.	Original study: >500 Kb, <1% frequency. Burden analysis: >200 Kb, <1% frequency.	Original study: Participants with vs without at least one CNV. Burden analysis: Deletion length, duplication length.	Original study: T-tests. Separate t-tests for full sample and sample with participants with ID removed. Burden analysis: Spearman's correlations.	Original study: With the full sample, carriers had lower IQ (P = 0.020) and reading ability (P = 0.020) than non-carriers. With participants with ID removed, CNV carriers had lower reading ability than non-carriers (P = 0.020), but not lower IQ. Burden analysis: non-significant trend towards association between deletion length and IQ (r = 0.08, P = 0.063).
van Scheltinga et al. 2013 ²⁸	Patients with schizophrenia and healthy controls.	672 (350 patients, 322 healthy controls.)	Patients with schizophrenia = 30.2 (9.0) Healthy controls = 31.6 (11.9)	IQ calculated from 4/11 subtests of the WAIS-III or WAIS-III-R. (block design, comprehension, vocabulary, picture arrangement).	Illumina HumanHap550 BeadChip array.	>9 markers. No frequency limit specified.	Duplication count, deletion count, number of genes affected by duplications, number of genes affected by deletions.	ANOVA, using duplication/deletion count, no. of genes affected by duplications/deletions, and clinical group as factors, and IQ as dependent variable. Separate ANOVAs for deletions and duplications.	No significant associations between CNV measures and IQ.
MacLeod et al. 2012 ²⁹	Healthy elderly people from 4 cohorts: Lothian birth cohort 1921, Lothian birth cohort 1936, the Aberdeen birth cohort 1936, and participants from the Manchester age and cognitive performance research centre programme.	Participants with a crystallised intelligence score = 3210. Participants with fluid intelligence score = 3133.	Mean ages for study sample not given. Mean ages of cohorts: Lothian 1921 = 79.1 (0.6), Lothian 1936 = 69.5 (0.8), Aberdeen 1936 = 64.6 (0.9), Manchester cohort = 65.6 (14.3)	Crystallised intelligence factor represented by NART or MHVT scores. Fluid intelligence factor derived from PCA of Moray house test, Raven's matrices, logical memory tests, verbal fluency tests, WASI-III, and RAVLT. (Different tests given to different cohorts). The 2 factors were corrected for age and sex.	Illumina610-Quad v1 chip array.	>500 Kb, 200-500kb and 100-200kb <1% frequency.	CNV count, duplication count, deletion count, CNV length, duplication length, deletion length, number of genes affected by duplications, number of genes affected by deletions.	Regressions, adjusted for cohort. T-tests compared the 2 intelligence factors between CNV carriers and non-carriers.	Regressions: no associations found between any of the CNV measures and either intelligence factor T-tests: no difference in either intelligence factors between CNV carriers and non-carriers.
Yeo et al.	Patients with schizophrenia and	189 (79 patients, 110	Patients with schizophrenia	A 'general cognitive ability' factor was	Illumina Human	>500 bp.	Deletion count, deletion length.	Regressions, adjusted for clinical group, age, sex,	Negative association between deletion count and general cognitive ability (beta = -0.19, p <0.001).

2013 ³⁰	healthy controls.	controls)	= 35.0 (11.4) Controls = 31.7 (10.9)	derived with a PCA from results of several tests, including reading ability, working memory, verbal abstraction, non-verbal reasoning, attention, visuo-motor skills, and executive skills.	Omni1-quad BeadChip array	<3% frequency.		ethnicity, and the interaction of deletion count/length with age and with clinical group.	
Huguet et al. 2018 ³¹	Adolescents from the IMAGEN study and children and their parents from the Saguenay Youth Study (SYS)	2711	IMAGEN cohort = 14.5 years (0.4) SYS cohort 610Kq Illumina = 14.5 years (1.9)* SYS cohort Human Omni Express Version 12 = 14.9 months (1.8)* *Average age only presented for the children	Performance IQ and Verbal IQ	IMAGEN cohort was genotyped using a combination of the Illumina 610Kq and 660Wq SYS cohort was genotyped using the Illumina 601Kq and HumanOmniExpress BeadChip V12	>50kb <0.1% frequency in the database of genomic variants or a non-recurrent CNVs with the following characteristics: (i) DGV frequency < 0.1%; (ii) < 50% of the CNV is contained in regions present at > 1% in DGV8-10; (iii) seen only once in each cohort	Deletion length, duplication length, number of genes affected by deletions, number of genes affected by duplications, number of exonic deletions and number of exonic duplications	Regressions, adjusted for first six principal components, sex, age, array and familial relatedness	Negative association between length of rare deletions and PIQ (standardised beta coefficient = -0.07, p = 0.000561). There was also evidence for an association between number of genes affected by rare deletions and PIQ (standardised beta coefficient = -0.06). No associations were found between rare duplications and PIQ for common deletions and duplications and either measure of IQ.
Guyatt et al. 2018 ³²	Children from the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents	4576 with IQ, including 85 carriers of	Exact values not given, IQ was assessed	IQ assessed with WISC at age 8	Illumina HumanHap 550-Quad	<1% >100kb	Number of genes affected by deletions, number	Regressions, adjusted for sex and first two principal components	IQ was associated with CNV burden: the SMD per gene affected by deletions was -0.019 (95% CI -0.028 to -0.009, p = 2e-04) and the SMD per gene

	and Children (ALSPAC)	known pathogenic CNVs	at age 8				of genes affected by duplications, length of deletions and length of duplications		affected by duplications was -0.016 (95% CI -0.024 to -0.008, p = 1e-04). IQ was also associated with CNV length. For the total length of CNVs, the SMD per 100kb of deletions was -0.035 (95% CI -0.048 to -0.022, p = 2e-07) and the SMD per 100kb of duplications was -0.012 (95% CI -0.01 to -0.003, p = 0.008).
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Note: Count refers to the number of CNVs of a given type, length refers to the number of bases affected by CNVs of a given type. CNV length/count refers to the length/count of all CNVs (both deletions and duplications).
Abbreviations: bp, Base pairs; Kb, kilo bases; WICS-R, Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – Revised; TOSCA, Test of Scholastic Abilities; BWRT, Burt Word Reading Test; WASI-I, Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale – I; WASI-III, Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale – III; WASI-IIIR, Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale – III Revised; MAB, Multidimensional Aptitude Battery; GWAS, Genome-Wide Association Study; NART, National Adult Reading Test; ADHD, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder; WORD, Wechsler Objective Reading Dimensions ID, Intellectual Disability; ANOVA, Analysis of Variance; MHVT, Mill Hill Vocabulary Test; PCA, Principal Components Analysis; RAVLT, Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test.

The 11 primary studies included in the systematic review and the sub-set of 10 contributing to the meta-analysis were diverse. Some studies included only healthy participants^{22,24,25,29,31}, whereas others included clinical samples^{23,26–28,30}. They also differed in sample size, age and gender distribution of participants. Nine of the papers examined the association between CNV burden and IQ, whereas two papers examined constructs other than ‘standard IQ’. MacLeod et al. 2012²⁹ measured a ‘fluid intelligence’ and a ‘crystallised intelligence’ factor, and Yeo et al. 2013³⁰ measured a ‘general cognitive ability’ factor. Both derived these factors from a principal components analysis of the results of several cognitive tests. Different measures of CNV burden were used, such as number or length of CNVs and examining duplication and deletions separate or together. Some studies specified a minimum length for a CNV to be included^{22,24,26–32}, others did not²³. Some studies only included CNVs with less than 1% frequency in their sample^{26,27,29,31,32}, others used a 5% cut-off^{22–25}. Six papers used correlations to investigate the association between CNV burden and IQ: two papers used Spearman’s correlations^{26,27} and four papers used Pearson’s correlations^{22–25}. Additionally, five papers reported regression analyses^{23,25,29–32}, one reported T-tests²⁷, and one reported an analysis of variance²⁸.

Supplementary Table 2: Participants from each centre with cognitive measures

Affiliation	City	Country	Cognitive Measures			
			Block Design	Digit Span	RAVLT Immediate Recall	RAVLT Delayed Recall
University of Edinburgh	Edinburgh	United Kingdom	42	36	0	0
GROUP Consortium (University of Amsterdam, University of Groningen, Maastricht University, University of Utrecht)	Amsterdam, Groningen, Maastricht, Utrecht	Netherlands	1307	0	1302	1285
Institute of Psychiatry, King's College London	London	United Kingdom	446	238	6	6
Ludwig-Maximilians, University of Munich	Munich	Germany	952	952	0	0
Fundacion Argibide, Pamplona	Pamplona	Spain	0	44	44	44
The University of Western Australia	Perth	Australia	0	0	554	554
Total			2747	1270	1906	1889

RAVLT = the Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Task.

Supplementary Table 3: Carriers of 27 schizophrenia-associated CNVs loci in the PEIC sample

Locus	Chromosome	Start Position(Hg18)	Stop Position(Hg18)	Size (Mb)	Gene of Interest	No. found	Odds Ratio	Frequency in controls	Reference
1q21.1.del	chr1	144800000	146326000	1.5		3	3.8-8.1	0.02-0.07	33-35
1q21.1.dup	chr1	144800000	146326000	1.5		0	2.9-4.2	0.03-0.07	33-35
2p25.3.dup	chr2	1733000	2204000	0.5	MYT1L	2	15.7		34
2p16.del	chr2	49900000	51500000	1.6	NRXN1	2	10.7-14.4	0.014	33-35
3q29.del	chr3	197185549	198838373	1.7	PAK2, DLG1	0	18-63	0-0.001	33-35
7q11.23	chr7	72380000	73780000	1.4		0	16.1	0.004-0.28	33,35
7q36.3.del	chr7	158448321	158810016	0.4	VIPR2	0	3.5	0.029	33
7q36.3.dup	chr7	158448321	158810016	0.4	VIPR2	2	3.2-3.5	0.029	33,34
8q22.2	chr8	100094670	100958984	0.9	VPS13B	0	14.5	0.004	33
9p24.3.del	chr9	831690	959090	0.1	DMRT1	0	12.4	0.004	33
9p24.3.dup	chr9	831690	959090	0.1	DMRT1	0	12.4	0.004	33
15q11.2.del	chr15	20301000	20824174	0.5	CYFIP1	7	1.8-2.1	0.25-0.27	33-35
15q11.2-13.1.dup	chr15	20322358	26208861	5.9		1	5.1		34,35
15q13.3.l.del	chr15	28723577	30303141	1.6	CHRNA7	1	4.7-15.6	0.009	33-35
15q13.3.ll.del	chr15	29806023	30407419	0.6	CHRNA7	0	14.9		34
16p13.11.dup	chr16	14897345	16199484	1.3	NTAN1, NDE1	5	2-2.2	0.13	34,35
16p13.11.del	chr16	15032942	16199484	1.2	NTAN1, NDE1	0	1.9		34
16p12.1.del	chr16	21854731	22331199	0.5		1	1.8		34
16p11.2.distal.del	chr16	28721599	28950951	0.2		0	2.6-20.6	0.004-0.01	33-35
16p11.2.del	chr16	29502984	30100062	0.6		2	0.5-0.9	0.04	34,35
16p11.2.dup	chr16	29531748	30105652	0.6		1	8-9.4	0.03	33-35
17p12.del	chr17	14041754	15411904	1.4		0	5.7	5.7	34
17q12.del	chr17	31889664	33323543	1.4	HNF1B	0	4-9.5	0.005	34,35
17q12.dup	chr17	31889664	33323543	1.4	HNF1B	0	2		34
22q11.21.large.del	chr22	17285281	19818855	2.5		1	67.7	0.04	33,35
22q11.21.del	chr22	19063495	19795780	0.7		1	Inf		34
Xq28.distal.dup	chrX	153800000	154225000	0.4		0	0.35	0.18	33

The loci comprise all schizophrenia associated loci from Marshall et al. 2016³³, Kirov et al. 2014³⁵ and Stefansson et al. 2014³⁴, excluding protective loci 22q11.21.dup, 7q11.21.del 7q11.21.dup, 13q12.11.dup, Xq28.dup. No. found indicate number of carriers found in the PEIC sample.

Supplementary Table 4: Assessments of study quality of primary studies

Assessments of study quality for studies meeting the inclusion criteria for the meta-analysis, using the quality assessment tool for observational, cohort, and cross-sectional studies from the National Institute of Health³⁶. Studies were assessed to be of similar quality. Two studies did not have uniformly-applied outcome measures for all participants^{28,29}.

Criteria		Bagshaw et al. 2013	Yeo et al. 2011	McRae et al. 2013	Kirkpatrick et al. 2014	Martin et al. 2014	Langley et al. 2011	van Scheltinga et al. 2013	MacLeod et al. 2012	Yeo et al. 2013	Huguet et al. 2018	Guyatt et al. 2018
1	Was the research question or objective in this paper clearly stated?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Was the study population clearly specified and defined?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Was the participation rate of eligible persons at least 50%?	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
4	Were all the subjects selected or recruited from the same or similar populations (including the same time period)? Were inclusion and exclusion criteria for being in the study prespecified and applied uniformly to all participants?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No ⁴	Yes	No ⁵	No (Point not deducted)	No ⁴	No ⁶ (Point not deducted)	No ⁷	Yes
5	Was a sample size justification, power description, or variance and effect estimates provided?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
6 ¹	For the analyses in this paper, were the exposure(s) of interest measured prior to the outcome(s) being measured?	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
7 ¹	Was the timeframe sufficient so that one could reasonably expect to see an association between exposure and	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	outcome if it existed?											
8	For exposures that can vary in amount or level, did the study examine different levels of the exposure as related to the outcome (e.g., categories of exposure, or exposure measured as a continuous variable)?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Original study: no. Burden analysis: yes.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	Were the exposure measures (independent variables) clearly defined, valid, reliable, and implemented consistently across all study participants?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
10 ¹	Was the exposure(s) assessed more than once over time?	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
11	Were the outcome measures (dependent variables) clearly defined, valid, reliable, and implemented consistently across all study participants?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ⁸	Yes	Yes ⁹	No ¹⁰	No ¹¹	Yes	No ¹²	Yes
12	Were the outcome assessors blinded to the exposure status of participants?	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
13 ²	Was loss to follow-up after baseline 20% or less?	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
14 ³	Were key potential confounding variables measured and adjusted statistically for their impact on the relationship between exposure(s) and outcome(s)?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

Ratings: Yes, No, NA (not applicable), NR (not reported), CD (cannot determine).

¹Criteria 6, 7, and 10 refer to the time-frame of assessing the exposure. All studies are marked NA for this because we know that CNVs are present and fixed at birth, therefore we know that the exposure (presence of CNVs) occurred before the outcome, so it doesn't matter if the exposure was assessed before the outcome (criteria 6).

Since CNVs are present at birth, we know that there will have been sufficient time for the association to have developed if it existed (criteria 7), and since CNVs are fixed and constant, there is no need to assess the exposure more than once over time (criteria 10).

² Criteria 13 is marked as NA for all studies because baseline and follow-up assessments were not necessary to measure the exposure (CNV burden) or outcome (IQ).

³ Age, sex, ethnicity and education level were regarded to be the key potential confounding variables.

⁴ Participants from cohorts of different ages were included in the study.

⁵ Some participants had intellectual disability, whereas others did not.

⁶ Both participants with schizophrenia and healthy controls were included. However, this was adjusted for in the analysis therefore a point was not deducted for this.

⁷ The study included adolescents from the IMAGEN study and children and parents from the Saguenay Youth Study.

⁸ Two different versions of the IQ test were used: the WISC-R (Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children - Revised) for participants aged <16, and the WAIS-R (Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale - Revised) for participants aged >16. This is because it would not be appropriate to test participants aged <16 with an adult IQ test or participants aged >16 with a children's IQ test, therefore this was not considered to be inconsistent implementation of outcome measures across participants, so this criteria was marked as a 'yes'.

⁹ The WORD (Wechsler Objective Reading Dimensions) assessment package was only given to participants aged <12, therefore was not implemented uniformly across study participants. However, this is not the outcome that we were interested in for the meta-analysis. Our outcome of interest, IQ, was assessed uniformly across participants, therefore this criteria was marked as a 'yes'.

¹⁰ Two different versions of the WAIS (Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale) were used: the WAIS-III and the WAIS-III-R (revised).

¹¹ Different outcome measures were given to the different cohorts included in the study.

¹² Two different versions of the IQ test were used: the WISC-IV edition was used in the IMAGEN cohort and the WISC-III was used for the SYS Cohort

Supplementary table 5: Comparisons between the sub-samples passing and failing QC

Parameter compared	Sub-sample passing QC N=4,294	Sub-sample failing QC N=1,303	Statistics
Clinical group distribution	55% patients 26% controls 19% relatives	49% patients 34% controls 17% relatives	P-value = 1 (Chi-squared test)
Sex	47.7% females	46.1% females	P-value = 0.33 (Chi-squared test)
Mean age (SD)	42.8 (15.6) years	37.8 (15.0) years	P-value = 4.8×10^{-20} (t-test)

Supplementary table 6: CNV burden in samples with and without cognitive data.

Burden	No Cognition or covariates available (N = 874)		Study sample (N = 3,428)	Wilcoxon rank-sum test
	Median number of genes affected (Q1-Q3)	Median number of genes affected (Q1-Q3)	Median number of genes affected (Q1-Q3)	p-value
CNV total	1 (0-6)	0 (0-2)	0 (0-2)	0.30
CNV duplications	0 (0-3)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0.27
CNV deletions	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0.82

Supplementary Table 7: Associations of clinical group and cognition, only including patients with a schizophrenia diagnosis

Predictor	Cognitive Measure	Participants (Associated CNV Carrier)	Regression Coefficient	95% CI	Sig.
Schizophrenia-associated CNVs	Block Design	2326 (18)	-9.787	-19.4, -0.186	0.046
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1541(22)	-8.39	-14.1, -2.72	0.004
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1524 (22)	-3.10	-5.82, -0.385	0.025
Genes affected by all CNVs	Block Design	2324	-0.117	-0.323, 0.090	0.268
	Digit Span	1188	0.026	-0.158, 0.210	0.780
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1539	-0.039	-0.181, 0.103	0.592
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1522	-0.025	-0.093, 0.043	0.474
Genes affected by deletions (deletion burden)	Block Design	2324	-0.440	-0.851, -0.029	0.036
	Digit Span	1188	-0.198	-0.662, 0.267	0.404
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1539	-0.115	-0.396, 0.166	0.423
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1522	-0.082	-0.216, 0.052	0.235
Genes affected by duplications (duplication burden)	Block Design	2324	-0.008	-0.245, 0.230	0.950
	Digit Span	1188	0.066	-0.131, 0.263	0.510
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	1539	-0.013	-0.177, 0.152	0.881
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	1522	-0.005	-0.084, 0.0073	0.895

Associations between known schizophrenia-associated CNVs and CNV burden with cognitive performance. For the schizophrenia associated CNV analysis digit span was not examined as fewer than 10 CNV carriers had available data. CNV burden was measured as number of genes affected by CNVs larger than >200 Kb, with <1% frequency. All analyses are adjusted for the covariates age, sex, clinical group, centre and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix).

Supplementary Table 8: Associations of clinical group with CNV burden measured as length

Predictor	Clinical group	Observations	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value
Length of all CNVs (total burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.302
	Relative vs Control	2658	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.303
Length of deletions (deletion burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.596
	Relative vs Control	2658	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.101
Length of duplications (duplication burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.371
	Relative vs Control	2658	1	-1.0, 3.0	0.962

All analyses were adjusted for gender, centre, age and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix). CNV burden was measured as the length of DNA affected by CNVs larger than >200 Kb, with <1% frequency.

Supplementary Table 9: Associations of CNV burden measured as length with cognitive performance

Predictor	Cognitive Measure	Regression Coefficient	95% CI	Sig.
Length of all CNVs (total burden)	Block Design	7.50E-04	1.88E-03, 3.73E+04	0.190
	Digit Span	-7.65E-05	1.2E-03, 1.10E+03	0.898
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	9.24E-05	7.2E-04, 9.03E+04	0.823
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	4.36E-05	3.42E-04, 4.29E+04	0.824
Length of deletions (deletion burden)	Block Design	1.79E-03	3.81E-03, 2.28E+04	0.082
	Digit Span	4.00E-04	2.9E-03, 2.11E+03	0.754
	RVLT Immediate Recall	1.12E-03	2.54E-03, 1.26E+03	0.121
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	6.20E-04	1.29E-03, 5.47E-05	0.072
Length of duplications (duplication burden)	Block Design	2.90E-04	1.65E-03, 1.08E+03	0.680
	Digit Span	1.38E-05	1.31E-03, 1.33E+03	0.984
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	6.86E+04	3.0E-04, 1.67E+03	0.174
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	3.71E+04	1.0E-04, 8.44E+03	0.123

Associations between CNV burden and cognitive performance. CNV burden was measured as Kb base pairs affected by CNVs larger than 200kb, with <1% frequency. All analyses adjusted for the covariates age, sex, clinical group, centre and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix).

Supplementary Table 10: Stratified subgroup analysis

Predictor	Cognitive Measure	Group	Participants (Associated CNV Carrier)	Regression Coefficient	95% CI	Sig.	
Schizophrenia-associated CNVs	Block Design	Patients	420 (5)	-26.2	-48.9, -3.51	0.024	
		Relatives	502 (2)	-16.5	-47.0, 13.9	0.288	
		Controls	1825 (14)	-1.94	-12.1, 8.26	0.709	
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	Patients	597 (10)	-11.8	-20.2, -3.38	0.006	
		Relatives	516 (2)	3.95	-14.2, 22.1	0.669	
		Controls	793 (12)	-6.18	-13.5, 1.14	0.098	
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	Patients	595 (10)	-4.64	-8.54, -0.727	0.020	
		Relatives	513 (2)	-1.23	-9.856, 7.40	0.781	
		Controls	781 (12)	-2.01	-5.50, 1.48	0.259	
Genes affected by all CNVs	Block Design	Patients	420	0.046	-0.556, 0.648	0.881	
		Relatives	502	-0.136	-0.648, 0.376	0.603	
		Controls	1825	-0.121	-0.333, 0.091	0.263	
	Digit Span	Patients	131	-0.278	-1.25, 0.696	0.576	
		Relatives	53	1.45	-0.350, 3.25	0.115	
		Controls	1086	0.0206	-0.167, 0.208	0.830	
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	Patients	597	0.143	-0.098, 0.384	0.243	
		Relatives	516	-0.09	-0.392, 0.212	0.561	
		Controls	793	-0.117	-0.291, 0.057	0.189	
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	Patients	595	0.055	-0.0566, 0.167	0.333	
		Relatives	513	0.043	-0.104, 0.190	0.565	
		Controls	781	-0.063	-0.146, 0.019	0.133	
	Genes affected by deletions (deletion burden)	Block Design	Patients	420	-0.909	-2.13, 0.309	0.143
			Relatives	502	-0.022	-1.14, 1.09	0.969
			Controls	1825	-0.413	-0.843, 0.017	0.060
Digit Span		Patients	131	0.383	-1.533, 2.30	0.695	
		Relatives	53	0.736	-1.77, 3.25	0.565	
		Controls	1086	-0.195	-0.666, 0.275	0.416	
RAVLT Immediate Recall		Patients	597	-0.092	-0.528, 0.343	0.678	
		Relatives	516	-0.333	-0.971, 0.305	0.307	
		Controls	793	-0.329	-0.718, 0.060	0.098	
RAVLT Delayed Recall		Patients	595	-0.07	-0.272, 0.132	0.498	
		Relatives	513	-0.215	-0.519, 0.089	0.165	
		Controls	781	-0.160	-0.345, 0.025	0.090	
Genes affected by duplications (duplication burden)		Block Design	Patients	420	0.366	-0.338, 1.07	0.308
			Relatives	502	-0.163	-0.733, 0.408	0.576
			Controls	1825	-0.027	-0.269, 0.215	0.826
	Digit Span	Patients	131	-0.465	-1.55, 0.615	0.399	
		Relatives	53	1.28	-1.02, 3.59	0.275	
		Controls	1086	0.060	-0.142, 0.261	0.561	
	RAVLT Immediate Recall	Patients	597	0.246	-0.042, 0.533	0.094	
		Relatives	516	-0.019	-0.359, 0.321	0.912	
		Controls	793	-0.063	-0.256, 0.131	0.526	
	RAVLT Delayed Recall	Patients	595	0.110	-0.024, 0.243	0.107	
		Relatives	513	0.121	-0.046, 0.287	0.155	
		Controls	781	-0.039	-0.131, 0.053	0.409	

Associations between known schizophrenia-associated CNVs and CNV burden with cognitive performance, only looking at one patient group at the time, either patients with psychosis, unaffected relatives or controls. For the schizophrenia associated CNV analysis digit span was not examined as fewer than 10 CNV carriers had available data. CNV burden was measured as number of genes affected by CNVs larger than >200 Kb, with <1% frequency.

Supplementary Table 11: Association between the CNV measures and clinical group

CNV Measure	Group	Schizophrenia-associated CNV carriers N (%)	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value
Schizophrenia-associated CNVs	Control	16 (0.8%)	1		
	Relative	2 (0.3%)	0.3	-4.0, 4.5	0.086
	Patient	12 (1.5%)	1.3	-1.8, 4.4	0.561
		Number of observations	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value
Genes affected (total CNV burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.516
	Relative vs Control	2658	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.307
Genes affected (deletion burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.516
	Relative vs Control	2658	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.143
Genes affected (duplication burden)	Patient vs Control	2780	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.784
	Relative vs Control	2658	1.0	-1.0, 3.0	0.672

All analyses were adjusted for gender, age, centre and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix). CNV burden was measured as number of genes affected by CNVs larger than >200 Kb, with <1% frequency.

Supplementary Table 12: Association between clinical group and cognitive performance

Cognitive Measure		N	Mean (SD)	Regression Coefficient	95% CI	P-value
Block Design	Control	1824	59.9 (21.3)	-	-	-
	Relative	502	51.7 (25.9)	-6.79	-9.3, -4.2	<0.0001
	Patient	419	53.0 (27.9)	-12.0	-14.6, -9.45	<0.0001
Digit Span	Control	1086	51.5 (14.6)	-	-	-
	Relative	53	41.7 (13.9)	-10.30	-14.8, -5.8	<0.0001
	Patient	131	48.2 (17.8)	-12.3	-16.2, -8.4	<0.0001
RAVLT Immediate Recall	Control	792	57.6 (13.8)	-	-	-
	Relative	516	56.1 (14.0)	-1.94	-3.5, -0.40	0.014
	Patient	596	49.3 (14.4)	-11.3	-12.9, -9.7	<0.0001
RAVLT Delayed Recall	Control	780	19.2 (6.4)	-	-	-
	Relative	513	19.1 (6.5)	0.31	-1.0, 0.4	0.408
	Patient	594	14.4 (6.8)	-4.7	-5.5, -3.9	<0.0001

The control group is the reference category. All analyses control for age, gender, centre and genetic relatedness (kinship matrix)

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Identifying common CNV loci

Supplementary Figure 1: Effect of bin-size on

number of unique loci. Determining CNV frequency by independent mapping of start and stop positions falling within a determined stretch of DNA (bin size in base pairs). Effect of altering bin size (the maximum distance between individual CNVs' start or stop positions for them to be considered as the same locus) on the number of unique independent CNV loci in the sample. Black = all CNVs, green = duplications only, red = deletions only. CNV algorithms estimate start and stop positions of CNVs in a non-exact way, and thus similar CNV loci may have slightly different start and stop positions in different carriers. This introduces a problem with determining exact CNV loci. In its extremes, either CNVs with slightly differing start and stop positions are collapsed into a single locus, or they are all treated as distinct loci. Here we tested the effect of altering the bin size used to map start and stop positions. As the bin size was increased, the number of unique independent CNV loci decreased. With smaller bin sizes, altering bin size had a large effect on the number of unique CNV loci, whereas with larger bin sizes, altering bin size had a smaller effect on the number of unique CNV loci. A bin size of 300 000 bp (indicated by the vertical dotted line) was chosen as a point where altering bin size began to have a smaller effect on the number on unique loci.

Supplementary Figure 2: PRISMA Diagram

Supplementary Figure 2: PRISMA diagram displaying literature search results. Medline and PsychINFO were searched simultaneously using the Ovid platform. All of the relevant papers returned by the Ovid search of Medline and PsychINFO (905 results) were also returned by the PubMed search, therefore only the PubMed search is described here. Screening of titles and abstracts revealed 13 papers that were assessed for eligibility: 12 of these examined the association between CNV burden and intelligence^{22,23,37,38,24–26,28–32}, and one²⁷ examined the difference in IQ between participants with and without large, rare CNVs. On request, Langley et al. 2011²⁷ provided the results of correlations between CNV burden and IQ, allowing these results to be included in the meta-analysis, and Hugué et al. 2018³¹ provided standardised beta coefficients. Martin et al. 2014³⁷ was not considered for inclusion, because the study uses the same sample of participants as Martin et al. 2014²⁶, which performs a burden analysis. Yeo et al. 2014³⁸ was not considered for inclusion as it used the same sample as Yeo et al. 2013³⁰. This left ten papers which examined the association between CNV burden and IQ^{22–30}.

Supplementary Figure 3: Additional meta-analysis forest-plots

Supplementary Figure 3: Forest plots for the meta-analyses investigating length of all CNVs (N=10,132), number of all CNVs (N=10,699), number of deletions (N=10,395), number of duplications (N=10,206), genes affected by deletions (N=10,420) and genes affected by duplications (N=10,420).

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